

THE THEORETICAL APPROACH OF CONCEPTS OF MODELS FOR QUALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN THE APPLICATION CONTEXT OF PUBLIC CONSTRUCTION ENTERPRISES

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Abstract

To build the effective model for implementation of quality management there is a need to identify elements of success and elements of no-success. Four means will be used in current study to design an effective and productive model for implementation of ISO-9000 standard: 1. Analysis of findings on implementation process of ISO-9000 standard in the 40 Local Authorities that participate in current study, by the interviews performed; 2. Questionnaires in which different quality managers, engineers and project managers were asked to rank the importance of subjects to successful instilling of ISO-9000 standard; 3. Statistical analysis of the multiple data gathered in interviews and from questionnaires; 4. A conference on the subject of implementation of ISO-9000 standard.

Key words: *ISO-9000, Management, Local Authorities, qualifying factor, perseverance, VE - Value Engineering Benefits of ISO-9000*

Analysis of Main Factors of Success in Implementing ISO-9000 Quality Standard

Introduction

One of the stated research goals was: proposing an effective model for implementation of quality management that will bring about the most benefit. To build such a model there is a need to identify elements of success and elements of no-success. [1, p. S463]. Four means will be used in current study to design an effective and productive model for implementation of ISO-9000 standard:

- The first means: analysis of findings on implementation process of ISO-9000 standard in the 40 Local Authorities that participate in current study, by the interviews performed. This analysis was done in sections 2.2.3 to 2.2.12. [1, p. S470].
- The second means: questionnaires in which different quality managers, engineers and project managers were asked to rank the importance of subjects to successful instilling of ISO-9000 standard, and to point out the key factors to produce the biggest benefit for the long-term from implementation of the ISO-9000 standard at their disposal. The results of these questionnaires will be in the next section, 2.3.
- The third means: statistical analysis of the multiple data gathered in interviews and from questionnaires. In this analysis this index will be designed. This index analysis will be presented in section 2.3.
- The fourth means: a conference on the subject of implementation of ISO-9000 standard, presented in next chapter, in which there was a discussion regarding different factors and their effect upon the success of implementation of ISO-9000 standard in engineering departments in Local Authorities. In the conference, the feedbacks on procedures suggested by the researcher were received, attached as appendix #6 of current study.

The Importance of Different Factors for Successful Instilling of ISO-9000 Standard: The quality managers in different Local Authorities and interviewed project

managers that had sufficient involvement in the implementation process, such as that which enables them to give their opinion, were asked to rank the importance of different subjects for successful instilling of the implementation process. The ranking in following table is according to a key attached to the table. [1, p. S470]. The question that was asked was on the importance of different subjects of ISO-9000 standard mainly, the answers should be regarded in this manner.

The subject that is most obvious above all other for successful instilling of ISO-9000 standard is involvement of Authority management, and the vast majority of repliers regard it as critical importance for success of implementation. The subject next in line of importance is involvement of project managers and employees of a Local Authority, but it is not stated what kind of involvement, be it in form of joint discussion or in form of formulating procedures. The third important subject is the instructions. From interviews with quality managers it can be said that many of them emphasized the subject, the term "perseverance" was also repeated in interviews with different project managers, and actually, all those are directed towards a thinking process of recognition and internalizing that all employees should go through. The next important subject is connected to all this which is feedback from employees. Many quality managers see the compatibility of the standard to the field as a very important thing, and feedback from employees helps this.

The next important subjects are subjects related to nature of the procedure in a decreasing order of magnitude are: early communication with the qualifying factor and establishment of a steering team. The qualifying factor of the Local Authorities participating in the study is the Israeli Institute of Standards. The Israeli Institute of Standards made a great and impressive effort to instill the ISO-9000 standard in the Israeli market and particularly to the construction branch in Local Authorities. [1, p. S467]. Part of this effort was training and instruction of Local Authorities' employees and probably due to that many consider an early connection with the qualifying factor as an important thing. An additional reason might be understanding the demands of the qualifying factor.

Table 1.1. Importance of Different Factors for Success of ISO-9000 Implementation

Subject	Critical importance	Very important	Important	Slightly important	Not important
Management involvement	65%	30%	8%	0%	0%
Instructions	20%	53%	33%	0%	0%
Establishing steering teams for quality	12%	30%	43%	13%	4%
Involvement of employees	25%	40%	27%	0%	2%
Feedback from clients	0%	22%	35%	35%	6%
Feedback from employees	8%	45%	36%	7%	3%
Early communication with the qualifying factor	8%	40%	35%	8%	4%
Contacting other Local Authorities	0%	5%	33%	25%	40%

Source: Author's research

It is not clear why so many recognize the importance of steering teams and so few create a real steering team. It might be that the perception of the term of steering team was

distorted under the influence of the researcher. The questionnaire was filled at the end of each interview and during the interview quality managers were asked regarding participants in steering teams as part of the implementation process. [1, p. S470]. Probably, the impression received was that quality manager and consultant constitute together a steering team. The question asked was: "is steering team including a quality manager and advisor only can be called a steering team or not?" In any case, it can be understood from the answer on importance of a steering team that leadership is very important to the implementation process, whether there is one person from the Authority in the steering team or a wider forum. [2, p. 36].

The subjects in lowest level of importance, in a decreasing order of magnitude are: feedback from clients and contacting other local authorities. Successful instilling of ISO-9000 standard in the Authority is an internal matter and is not dependent too much on external factors including clients, and these answers are logical. The importance of feedback from clients can produce a bigger benefit from the quality system but it is not connected to its instilling.

Summary: In the opinion of quality managers, successful instilling of ISO-9000 standard is dependent mainly on involvement of management of the Authority, involvement of employees and training for employees. Leadership and early communication with the qualifying factor are important as well, however less. [1, p. S467].

Factors to Produce Maximal Benefit from Implementation: All the interviewees and other position holders (especially quality managers) from Local Authorities were asked what, in their opinion, is the key to produce maximal benefit, for the long-term, from implementation of ISO-9000 standard at their disposal. The respondents to this question had to choose from a number of choices, as described in table 2.25. Surely the wording of the question is aimed at choosing a single key factor; however, an option to choose more than one key factor was given. As can be seen, one of the key factors suggested in the questionnaire is not under the control of Local Authorities, and it is: combining of many factors in the Local Authority to a chain of quality.

Table 3.2.: Key Factors and Maximum Benefits of ISO-9000 According to the Interviewees and other Position Holders from Local Authorities Participating in the Research

	Inclusion of employees	Joining of Local government	Simple and concise procedures	Current operation of teams	Employing ISO-9000 standard for implementing TQM	Utilizing information on malfunctions for improvement
Quality managers	60%	45%	70%	40%	4%	85%
Interviewed managers	30%	33%	47%	46%	0%	74%

Source: Author's research

In ranking importance of the key factors according to number of questionnaires respondents who pointed them out, it can be seen that the first and foremost key factor for successful implementation of ISO-9000 standard is utilizing information on complaints to improve quality. This answer testifies mainly to the fact that the questionnaires respondents understand the subject of quality and the principle of prevention as part of the role of a quality system. However, all Authorities participating in the study, with exception of one, have not started yet collection and analysis of data on the complaints.

The second important key factor, regarding which there is as well a consensus between quality managers and the interviewees in the sites, is: concise and simple to

execute procedures. As mentioned above, the main difficulty in working with the procedures, formulated following the implementation of ISO-9000 standard are: abundance of paper and bureaucracy and a high consumption of time. Formulating concise and easy to execute procedures will make facilitate from this aspect, and in the opinion of many of them will make the implementation of ISO-900 standard useful. Formulating concise procedures, especially concise tagging lists, may bring about a lack of proper documentation of malfunctions that are discovered while the process of execution, and there will be more need to rely more on repair actions as the primary means of documentation.

Interesting finding discovered in this questionnaire, is a different addressing of quality managers on one hand, and interviewees in the sites on the other hand, to participation of employees from all levels in shaping the procedures. While most quality managers think that participation of employees in all levels in shaping the procedures constitutes a key to success, most of the interviewees in the field think differently. All interviewees that were not involved in formulating the procedures, except for one, think that such involvement does not constitute a key to success. As opposed to this, amongst interviewees in sites that were involved in formulating the procedures there are opinions hither and thither.

Another important subject is joining of a Local Authority to the quality chain. Many are aware of the fact that as more factors join the quality chain, the implementation of ISO-9000 standard will be more successful in their organization, specifically.

ISO-9000 standard can serve as a basis for implementation of total quality management, but it appears that almost comprehensively the questionnaire respondents think that they don't see in that option a key to achieve benefit from the standard. [3, p. 463].

As opposed to it, many think that operating teams to improve quality can constitute a key for achievement of most benefit from ISO-9000 standard. It is worth mentioning that the interviewees and the questionnaires respondents were not tested on their knowledge and their orientation in subject of quality, but from talking to some of them it appears that many don't know what are quality circles or total quality management (TQM). Despite this, something is positive in the fact that many consider positively the establishment of teams to improve quality, that indicates openness and a desire to extend the quality system and to broaden its efficiency, even assuming that they do not mean quality circles.

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